

The band at $\sim 15\,030\text{ cm}^{-1}$ is attributed to ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ transition. The band at $\sim 17\,380\text{ cm}^{-1}$ can be unambiguously interpreted to arise due to ligand field transition of the octahedral component of the Co^{II} complex and may be assigned to transition ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$ in an approximately octahedral field. The band at $24\,400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to charge transfer.

The magnetic moment of the Mn^{II} complex is 5.89 B.M. Its electronic spectrum shows band at $\sim 18\,000$, $25\,100$ and $27\,500\text{ cm}^{-1}$ suggesting an octahedral geometry around the central metal ion and may be attributed to transition ${}^6A_{1g}(S) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(G)$, $\rightarrow {}^4E_g + {}^4A_{1g}(G)$ and $\rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(D)$ respectively. This is in accordance with the earlier reported values for Mn^{II} ion⁶.

The room temperature magnetic moment value of the VO^{II} complex (0.513 B.M.) is abnormally lower than the spin-only value (1.73 B.M.), which may be due to the presence of exchange coupled antiferromagnetism. The VO^{II} complex exhibits three bands at $\sim 12\,200$, $15\,600$ and $22\,700\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which may be assigned to $e_g \rightarrow b_{2g}$, $e_g \rightarrow a_{1g}$ and $e_g \rightarrow b_{1g}$ transitions respectively. These transitions are based on octahedral symmetry with tetragonal distortion, the elongation being on Z-axis⁷.

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Neutral Complexes of Platinum(II) and Palladium(II) with 2,2'-Dipyridylamine and 2,2'-Dipyridylketone

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CONSIDERABLE interest has recently been evinced in the complexes of platinum and palladium, mainly due to their possible utilisation as potential

anticancer drugs¹. In persuasion to our work in this area²⁻⁴, we report herein the complexes of 2,2'-dipyridylamine and 2,2'-dipyridylketone with platinum(II) and palladium(II).

Experimental

K_2PtCl_4 , K_2PdCl_4 , 2,2'-dipyridylamine (dpa) and 2,2'-dipyridylketone (dpk) (Aldrich) were used as such. All other chemicals were of reagent grade. Solvents were purified and dried prior to use.

Complexes $[\text{M}(\text{dpa})/(\text{dpk})\text{X}_2]$ were prepared by adding concentrated methanolic solution of dpa/dpk (1 mmol) to an aqueous solution (20 ml) of $\text{K}_2\text{PtCl}_4/\text{K}_2\text{PdCl}_4$ (1 mmol) excess of KX ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}^-$, Br^- , or I^-) with vigorous stirring⁵. The complexes (precipitated immediately or after several hours) were washed successively with water, methanol and acetone, recrystallised from 1:1 DMF-water mixture and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride, (60–90%).

Complexes $[\text{M}(\text{dpa/dpk})(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)]$ were prepared^{6,7} by adding concentrated methanolic solution of dpa/dpk (1 mmol) to an aqueous solution (20 ml) of $\text{K}_2\text{M}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The resulting solution was stirred for 24 h and its pH was maintained slightly acidic. The resulting solid was washed with water and dry ether, and dried under reduced pressure over anhydrous calcium chloride, (~50%).

The details of physical and spectroscopic measurements of the compounds were similar to those described earlier²⁻⁴.

Results and Discussion

Analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. All the complexes are insoluble in water and other common solvents, however, they are appreciably soluble in coordinating solvents such as DMF and DMSO. The molar conductances of the complexes in DMF solutions, range from 3 to $21\ \Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$, indicating their non-electrolytic nature⁸. All the complexes are diamagnetic in nature, as expected, indicating square-planar configuration.

The electronic absorption spectra of 2,2'-dipyridyl ketone complexes exhibit bands at 34.7–36.5 (broad, $\epsilon = 0.9 - 1.1 \times 10^4$) and 28–29.4 kK ($\epsilon = 0.13 - 0.16 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). These bands can be tentatively assigned to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions of the ligand and metal to ligand charge transfer (MLCT) transition respectively. In case of the 2,2'-dipyridylamine complexes $\pi-\pi^*$ transition bands appear at 36.8–37.2 ($\epsilon = 1.1 - 1.3 \times 10^4$) and 33.8–24.1 kK ($\epsilon = 1.2 - 1.4 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$) while MLCT band appears at 28.5–29.1 kK ($\epsilon = 0.3 - 0.46 \times 10^4\text{ dm}^3\text{ mol}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$). A weak band assignable to singlet to triplet transition is also observed at 24–25 kK in these complexes⁹.

The ir spectra (KBr) complexes were recorded in the range $4\,000 - 200\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$ band at

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
		N	M ^a	X ^b
Pt(dpa)I ₂	Yellow	6.52 (6.77)	31.97 (31.45)	40.73 (40.96)
Pd(dpa)I ₂	Yellow	7.74 (7.90)	19.52 (19.96)	47.57 (47.83)
Pt(dpa)Br ₂	Yellow orange	8.02 (7.98)	37.12 (37.02)	30.17 (30.41)
Pd(dpa)Br ₂	Yellow	7.53 (7.61)	24.18 (24.25)	35.45 (36.61)
Pt(dpa)Cl ₂	Light yellow	9.60 (9.61)	44.48 (44.62)	15.94 (16.26)
Pd(dpa)Cl ₂	Bright yellow	12.28 (12.06)	30.50 (30.45)	20.28 (20.40)
Pt(dpa)OX	Yellow	9.43 (9.24)	42.87 (42.95)	—
Pd(dpa)OX	Yellow	11.56 (11.50)	29.23 (29.04)	—
Pt(dpk)I ₂	Orange yellow	4.18 (4.42)	30.71 (30.80)	39.98 (40.12)
Pd(dpk)I ₂	Yellow	5.27 (5.14)	19.33 (19.48)	46.54 (46.69)
Pt(dpk)Br ₂	Yellow brown	4.98 (5.19)	86.25 (86.17)	29.36 (29.69)
Pd(dpk)Br ₂	Yellow	6.37 (6.22)	23.36 (23.55)	35.46 (35.55)
Pt(dpk)Cl ₂	Yellow	6.10 (6.22)	43.18 (43.33)	15.52 (15.77)
Pd(dpk)Cl ₂	Yellow orange	7.50 (7.75)	29.29 (29.36)	19.51 (19.66)
Pt(dpk)OX	Yellow	5.59 (5.99)	41.80 (41.75)	—
Pd(dpk)OX	Yellow	7.28 (7.40)	28.10 (28.04)	—

^aM = Pt or Pd. ^bX = Cl, Br or I.

~ 1580 cm⁻¹ in free ligands (dpa/dpk) shows a slight positive shift in all the complexes suggesting the chelation of the ligands to the metal via pyridine ring nitrogen atoms^{10,11}. This is further supported by the positive shifts of other ring breathing modes in the complexes as compared to those in the free ligands. The ν_{NH} and δ_{NH} vibration of dpa at 3300 and 1603 cm⁻¹ respectively and $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ vibration of dpk at 1680 cm⁻¹, are not appreciably affected in the platinum and palladium complexes. This clearly indicate that NH of dpa and CO of dpk are not involved in metal binding. The analogous chloro complexes of Pt^{II} show two medium-intense to intense absorption bands at about 345 and 330 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu_{\text{Pt-Cl}}$ asymmetric and symmetric vibrations respectively, corresponding to two chloro groups in the *cis*-position^{12,13}. In case of the Pd^{II} complexes $\nu_{\text{Pd-Cl}}$ vibrations appear at about 325 and 310 cm⁻¹ respectively. The $\nu_{\text{M-Br}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-I}}$ vibrations appear at ~ 250 and ~ 200 cm⁻¹ respectively and hence have not been assigned. The presence of bands at ~ 1700, ~ 1650, ~ 1400, ~ 920 and ~ 820 cm⁻¹ in oxalato complexes suggests the bidentate oxalate ion coordination to platinum and palladium¹⁴.

The ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆) were recorded using TMS as internal standard. The polypyridyl ligand proton signals were assigned following the ¹H nmr assignments of α - α' -diimine ligands^{15,16}. The H-6,6' proton signal of 2,2'-dipyridylamine

appearing as a doublet at δ 8.24, shifted to δ 8.24–9.14 in the platinum complexes and to δ 8.7–9.00 in the palladium complexes; while in case of 2,2'-dipyridylketone, the H-6,6' proton signal appearing at δ 8.74 as a doublet, shifted to δ 9.19–9.46 and 9.05–9.31 in the platinum and palladium complexes respectively. The shifts follow a trend, δ -chloro < δ -bromo < δ -iodo. The large downfield shifts of H-6,6' protons together with downfield shifts of other ligand protons, clearly indicate ligand binding to metal via pyridine rings. This is further confirmed by large values of ²J_{Pt-H} coupling constants (44–50 Hz) for ¹⁹⁵Pt–N–C–H fragments for the platinum complexes.

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Studies on Quaternary Complexes of some Lanthanones

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It is interesting to note¹⁻⁵ that in the formation of mixed ligand species, the trivalent lanthanides have a tendency to attain their unusual coordination number forming more stable complexes. This